

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

COMPOUND WORDS IN THE KARAKALPAK LANGUAGE

Bekbergenov Q.

*candidate of philological sciences,
Senior Researcher, Karakalpak Research Institute
of Humanities Karakalpak Branch of the
Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan, Nukus*

Abstract

The article analyzes the composite words in the Karakalpak language. They have been used in Karakalpak grammar as different words, sometimes compound words, and sometimes separate words. The author comes to the conclusion that it is correct to call them as composite words. The article also proves the difference of compound words from free phrasal verbs and phraseologisms.

Keywords: Turkic languages, Karakalpak language, compound words, composite words, features of composite words, word combination.

Compound words form a large group of complex words. They are the first step in the conversion of word combinations into compound words.

Although compound words are studied as much as possible in turkological literature, their composition, types, and even the names are interpreted in different ways. For example, N. A. Baskakov [1, c. 184-185], K. Sabirov [2, c. 156-157] and other scholars used the term "compound word", S. N. Muratov calls all kinds of scientific and technical terms, geographical terms, names of office, book, newspaper, magazine, and other names as lexicalized set phrases. For example: *Alis konsigich*, (*Far East*) *Aral dīngeze* (*Aral Sea*) *balalar baqsahu* (*kindergarden*) [3, c. 98].

K. Akhanov called compound words in the Kazakh language as *kürdeli-qurama sózler* in recent works they were called *tirkessen kürdeli sózler*. In works on the Uzbek language, compound and conjoint words are called as compound words with one word. B. Madaliev used the term "tarkibli suzlar" for composite words and clarified their features and classified them in terms of meaning.

N. A. Baskakov considers the words *qizil úy* (*red house*), *janiwar* (*creature*), *jorg'a jurmel* (*racehorse*), *qara qus* (*black bird*), *qisqish shayan* (*cancer*), *tasbaqa* (*tortoise*), *qurbaqa* (*frog*), *shashbaw* (*hair ribbon*), *qolqap* (*gloves*), *qol jazba* (*manuscript*), *belbew* (*belt*) at *arba* (*horse carriage*), *kempir quyash* (*rainbow*), *kindik sheshe* (*godmother*), *jalmawiz kempir* (*witch*), *adamzat* (*humanity*), *ógey bala* (*stepson*), *ógey qız* (*stepdaughter*), *qaym ata* (*father-in-law*), *qaym ene* (*mother-in-law*) etc. In the Karakalpak language, as compound nouns that cannot be separated from the lexical point of view, and denote one entire meaning: (pp. 184-185), words like *jalañ ayaq* (*barefoot*), *jalañ bas bareheaded*), *jalañash* (*naked*) as compound adjectives (p. 209), fractional numbers are considered as compound numbers (p. 229), sequence of verbs and auxiliary verbs that come in the form of infinitive as compound verbs (p. 323).

A. Kidirbayev included compound words and the word combinations in Karakalpak language - *temir jol* (*railway*) and the words with izafet connection- *taw burkiti*, (*mountain golden eagle*), *Aral teñizi* (*Aral sea*)

, *xaliq sudi* (*people's court*) into the compound nouns combined by syntactic method. And combined compound nouns include "the names of the country and party organs, offices and organizations, which are combined from several words" [4, c. 58-59]. For example: *Karakalpakstan Joqarǵi Soveti* (*Supreme Soviet of Karakalpakstan*) etc.

In recent works on the Karakalpak language, compound words are called *sostavli sozler* (compound words) and in school grammar they are called "separate words". In our opinion, the term "compound words" cannot be considered correct, because it contradicts the common meaning of the compound words: if the words are not combined, the question how they are compound words may arise. The term "compound words" is taken from the works written in Russian, instead of it the term "compound words" can be fully used, because they express one meaning from two or more separate words.

In Karakalpak and other Turkic languages, the boundaries of compound words, their difference from other types of words and word combinations are not sufficiently revealed. Sometimes they are considered separately, sometimes viewed with other kinds of compound words. Their names are not common either. Therefore, it is necessary to define their main features.

Compound words in the modern Karakalpak language easily differ from conjoint, pair and repeated words by their structure. Basically, they are close to independent set phrases, because composite words, as we explained, are the first stage in the transformation of a phrase into compound words. However, they are distinguished from word stems by their characteristic features:

1) The words in the word combination are united from the semantic and grammatical point and form one grammatical unit - the word combination, and the components of the words (although orthographically they are written separately) are united semantically and form one lexical unit [5, c. 45]. Compare: *Sóz bası hám adamnıñ bası*, *awıl xojalıǵı hám awıldnıñ jigiteri t.b.* (*The head of the word and the head of a person, agriculture and the village guys etc.*)

2) The components of the compound words are closely connected and cannot be separated from each

other or interpreted by mixing words between them; The words in the word combination are to some extent free, they can be replaced by another word or interpreted by choosing another word between them. Compare: *соқыр ишек хәм соқыр ғарры (соқыр болған ғарры, ғарры соқыр (blind gut and blind old man)*

3) Since the compound words are originated from word combinations, and they were used in that form for a long time, syntactic connection (attributive or object relation) between their components disappeared and the word combination lexicalized and became compound word. Also semantic relationship between the components disappears and one of them (in most cases, the first component) deviates from its original single meaning when standing separately, it only denotes the meaning when accompanied by other components. For example: *tas bawır* (“stone heart”- cruel), *kók bet* (quarrelsome), *kempir quyash* (rainbow), *kún kóris* (subsistence) etc.

4) In the sentence the word combination is divided into different parts of the sentence; Since compound words are pronounced with one stress and, they perform the function of only one member. Therefore we cannot put questions to the components of compound words. For example: *Temir qazıq - an iron stake (you can't guess what kind of stake)* and so on.

5) The components of the word combination are only connected in the process of speaking. The components of the compound words are pre-formed, ready-made material, so they are stable.

6) The components of the word combination are divided into different parts of speech, and compound word belongs to only one part of speech, and in the process of word change it has affixes belonging to that part of speech.

7) It is not possible to shorten the components of compound words or their affixes.

These are the main features that separate compound words from free word combinations.

The components of the compound words are closely connected from the beginning and they became stable words, therefore, the compound words are close to phraseological units. Some researchers even consider them as phraseology [6, c. 171-172], but there are noticeable differences between the compound words and phraseological units:

1) Compound words (especially compound terms) are used in the nominative function (as name of the subject) and do not have expressiveness. Idiomaticity, expressiveness is the main feature of phraseological units.

2) Phraseologisms are expressive equivalents, synonyms of one single word [7, c.73]. For example: *at ústi - ústirtin (superficially); kózdi ashıp jumǵansha -*

júdá tez (very quickly, fast). Compound terms have only one meaning and do not have synonyms.

Although the structure words and phraseologisms have only these differences, there is a closeness between them. Especially attributive phraseologisms are close to the compound adjectives and adverbs. Therefore, some (often two-component) attributive phraseologisms should be considered from the morphological point of view in the structure of compound adjectives and adverbs. Such phraseologisms, are synonymous with words the part of speech to which those words belong, and have the form-changing affixes of that part of speech [8, c. 75-76]. For example: *tas bawır (miyrimisiz, qatal) - júdá tas bawır, tas bawırlaw; (“stone heart”- ruthless, cruel; er júrek (márt) - er júreklew, er júrekli-rek, júdá er júrek; (brave- braver-bravest); bir shetkey (bólek) - bir shetkeylew, dim bir shetkey; (separate-more separate, the most separate); alıp satar (sawdager) - alıp satarlar, alıp satarıńız, alıp satarǵa, alıp satarıń t.b. (profiteer - profiteers, your profiteer, to profiteer, you are a profiteer etc)*.

Thus, compound words appear to express some kind of complex and new meaning. They originate as free expressions and are used in that form for long, became stable and then turn into compound words.

In the development of society, many new compound words have been created to express any new and compound meanings in the fields of science, technology, culture, industry, agriculture. Such words in the Karakalpak language, especially during the soviet times, were formed to express new notions under the influence of the Russian language. When used in the Karakalpak language, the Russian compound or complex words created compound words with new meaning: *linguistics, submarine, agenda, relative weight, automatic telephone, agriculture, etc.*

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